

QUALITY IMPROVING OF LOCAL SPROCKETS USING THE PACK CARBURIZING METHOD WITH HOLDING TIME VARYING

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Abstract

Sprockets are spare parts on motorbikes that work by transmitting power to the rear tire of the motorbike. Various sprocket products are sold on the market, ranging from standard original products from Japanese manufacturers which are quite expensive to locally made ones with relatively cheap prices. In order to compete with Japanese manufactured sprocket products, it is necessary to improve the mechanical properties of local sprockets so that the quality of local sprockets approaches or exceeds Japanese manufactured sprockets, but at a low price. This research aims to produce locally made sprockets so that the quality can approach or exceed original Japanese manufactured sprockets at a relatively cheap price. The method used for surface hardening is pack carburizing, the carburizing temperature is at 920°C with holding times varying to 15, 30, 45 and 60 minutes. The carbon material used is coconut shell charcoal, then the catalyst used is beef bone (CaCO₃) with a ratio of 85% carbon and 15% catalyst. The results of the tests that have been carried out show that there has been an increase in the mechanical properties of the local carburized sprocket as time increases. The 15 minute holding time specimen had a layer thickness of 265.77 μm, a hardness value of 405.84 HV and a wear rate of 360 10⁻⁶ gr/minute; the 30 minute holding time specimen had a layer thickness of 346.55 μm, a hardness value of 188.81 HV and a wear rate of 257 10⁻⁶ gr/minute; the 45 minute holding time specimen had a layer thickness of 935.47 μm, a hardness value of 277.37 HV and a wear rate of 243 10⁻⁶ gr/minute; The most optimal specimen with a holding time of 60 minutes has a layer thickness of 452.42 μm, a hardness value of 407.44 HV and a wear rate of 97 10⁻⁶ gr/minute. These results have shown an increase in the mechanical properties of the specimen so that the quality of local sprockets approaches or even exceeds the quality of original Japanese manufactured sprockets but at a relatively cheap price.

Keywords: *Predictive Maintenance, Preventive Maintenance, wear, Hertzian contact, Ball bearing*

1. Introduction

Technological developments in the automotive motorcycle manufacturing industry continue to grow rapidly in line with the needs of the Indonesian market, which is the third largest country in the world in terms of the number of motorbike riders [1, 2, 3]. So, on this basis the demand for motorbike spare parts is increasing along with the increase in the number of vehicles. The sprocket is an important component on a motorbike which must have hardness on the edges of its teeth so that it does not wear out easily due to friction with the chain. There are various kinds of sprocket products available on the market, ranging from expensive Japanese manufacturers to more affordable local sprockets. To compete with Japanese sprockets, it is necessary to improve the mechanical properties of local sprockets so that the quality approaches or exceeds Japanese-made sprockets at a relatively cheap price.

In order to meet this need, the researcher decided to use the pack carburizing method because it is a surface hardening treatment technique by adding carbon elements to the surface of the material which is simple and cheap to work with [3, 4, 5].

Research on 1025 steel to see the effect of holding time for the carburizing process on steel hardness with varying holding times, namely 60, 90 and 120 minutes. The highest hardness result was 105.07 HRB, for a sample with a holding time of 120 minutes with water cooling media [6, 7, 8]

Research on S35C steel was carried out pack carburizing using wood charcoal as carbon and then egg shells as a source of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) which functions as a catalyst. The variation in this research is holding time. The results obtained after carrying out the research process used a mixture ratio of 60% carbon (wood charcoal) and 40% catalyst used in this case egg shell (CaCO_3) from 1 kg of carburizing media, with holding times varying to 15 minutes, 30 minutes, and 45 minutes. There was an increase in the hardness value obtained in the 15 minute specimen to 6.6 HRC; 30 minutes 14.33; 45 minutes 28.62 HRC [4, 9, 10].

Research carried out on carburized SS400 steel using coconut shell carbon as carbon and BaCO_3 as a catalyst. The changes made are related to temperature and storage time. The results of this test at a temperature of 955°C and holding for 3 hours showed the highest hardness, namely 868.3 HV. It can be stated that hardness increases with the length of holding time [11, 12].

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research procedure

In this research, researchers conducted an experimental study which aims to determine changes in the mechanical properties of local sprockets after pack carburizing and holding time variations and to produce local sprocket products that have quality close to or exceeding Japanese manufactured sprockets at relatively cheap prices. [13, 14, 15]

The materials used are local sprockets and sprockets made in Japan (YGP), the heat treatment method used is pack carburizing with a carbon and catalyst ratio of 85% coconut shell charcoal and 15% beef bone powder (CaCO_3). The heating temperature is 920°C with varying holding times, namely 15, 30, 45 and 60 minutes as well as a fast cooling method using water as a medium.

The local sprocket is fully annealed to remove the properties produced by the previous treatment process [2]. Then, the two types of sprockets were cut into 5 pieces for local sprockets and 1 piece for Japanese-made sprockets, then the composition was tested on local sprocket specimens to determine the carbon content.

The solid carburizing process for the 4 local sprocket specimens was carried out at a temperature of 920°C with varying holding times, namely 15, 30, 45 and 60 minutes. After cooling the carburizing process, in order to obtain optimum mechanical properties, rapid cooling is carried out using water as a medium.

Fig. 1 Raw material after cutting

After the specimen is carburized, the installation of tools or mountings is carried out in accordance with ASTM E407, then metallographic testing (microstructural testing), hardness testing and wear testing are carried out. Metallography was carried out on sprocket specimens made in Japan and local sprockets that had been carburized and uncarburized, as well as hard tests but wear tests that did not involve non-treated local sprockets.

Fig. 2 Local sprocket after carburizing

Carbon composition examination using an Optical Emission Spectrometer. The etching solution used in metallography was 3% nital, the structure was examined using an optical microscope and the data obtained were the microstructure and total case depth calculated vertically from the edge of the coated surface to the boundary of the unhardened layer. Hardness test according to ASTM E384 using Vickers Microhardness with a load of 100gr and sequential indentation points from the edge area to the core. The wear test was carried out using the pin on disk method with the G99 test standard, the pressing load was 3.5 Kg and the disk used AISI52100 with a rotation speed of 900 RPM.

Fig. 3 The sprocket has been installed on the mounting

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the composition tests carried out, it was found that the local sprocket used was alloy steel with a low carbon content, namely 0.060%. The following is the test table:

Table 1 OES (Optical Emission Spectrometer) test results

NO	Unsur / Element	Wt. %
1	Carbon (C)	0,060%
2	Silicon (Si)	0,125%
3	Sulfur (S)	0,034%
4	Phosphorus (P)	0,042%
5	Manganese (Mn)	0,469%
6	Nickel (Ni)	0,000%
7	Chromium (Cr)	0,010%
8	Molybdcnum (Mo)	0,006%
9	Vanadium (V)	0,000%
10	Copper (Cu)	0,004%
11	Wolfram/Tungsten (W)	0,001%
12	Titanium (Ti)	0,002%
13	Tin (Sn)	0,001%
14	Aluminium (Al)	0,001%
15	Plumbun/Lead (Pb)	0,000%
16	Antimony (Sb)	0,000%
17	Niobium (Nb)	0,000%
18	Zirconium (Zr)	0,000%
19	Zinc (Zn)	0,000%
20	Ferro/Iron (Fe)	99,249%

Metallographic (microstructural) testing carried out on sprockets made in Japan showed that they had previously undergone special treatment, namely hot rolling, so that the shape of the ferrite and pearlite phase grains tended to be elongated and flat with layers that had been hardened quite deeply with an average hardness value of 252.38 HV. In contrast to sprockets made in Japan, in the microstructure of non-treated local sprockets there is only a ferrite phase and pearlite grain boundaries (lamellar) with a predominance of ferrite grains and without any hardened layers and the average hardness value is 126.33 HV.

Fig. 4 Microstructure (A) Japanese (B) Local

In carburized specimens there are also differences in microstructure due to different holding times and conditions during the rapid cooling process. The results of this test can be seen in Fig. 5. From Fig. 5 it can be seen that the 15 minute specimen not only contains pearlite and ferrite phases, but also carbide and has an average hardness value of 405.84 HV. In the 30 minute specimen there was no significant change from the specimen before treatment, only the pearlite became thicker with an average hardness value of 188.81 HV. In the 45 minute specimen, the structure formed is proeutectoid ferrite along with Widmanstatten morphology [6] with an average hardness value of 277.37 HV. In the 60 minute specimen, the base structure formed a closed or broken ferrite phase and spheroidized pearlite with an average hardness value of 407.44 HV.

Fig. 5 Microstructure of carburized specimens with variations in holding time

The results of the microstructure (Metallography) test show that there is an unevenness in the carburization results. There are many factors that cause this apart from differences in holding time, namely the uneven mixing and distribution of carbon in the area around the specimen and causing a thick layer on one side (unbalanced). However, if you look at the trend line in Figure 6, it shows that the average layer thickness is higher if the holding time is longer. This is because carbon needs time to diffuse into the specimen and will cause the carbon to diffuse deeper into the surface of the specimen.

Fig. 6 Chart of layer thickness of carburized specimen

Fig. 7 Graph of Violence Rates against Time

It can be seen in Figure 7 that the trendline shows that the longer the holding time, the specimen tends to have a higher hardness value. This is because the length of holding time affects the amount of carbon elements that are diffused, causing an increase in the hardness of the specimen and the formation of carbide compounds. The thickness of the carburizing layer and structural density can be formed due to the addition of carbon elements so that the hardness of the specimen increases.

Fig. 8 Wear Test Results

No	Kode Sampel	Berat (gram)			Waktu Uji (menit)	Wear Rate (gram/menit)
		Sebelum Uji	Sesudah Uji	Weight Loss		
1	Ori	5,6731	5,6677	0,0054	30	0,000180
2	15	5,5577	5,5469	0,0108	30	0,000360
3	30	6,0651	6,0574	0,0077	30	0,000257
4	45	4,7783	4,771	0,0073	30	0,000243
5	60	5,6510	5,6452	0,0058	30 x 2	0,000097

Wear testing is carried out on the tooth edge or tip of the sprocket tooth of each specimen according to the actual conditions of use of the sprocket. It can be seen in Table 2 that the local sprocket with a resistance time of 60 minutes was tested twice to ensure that the wear value was not wrong because it was very different from the wear value of Japanese-made sprockets. From the results of this test, it was found that local sprockets that had been carburized experienced a decrease in wear value as the holding time increased, meaning that the longer the holding time, the higher the wear resistance value.

This is because the length of holding time affects the amount of carbon elements that can diffuse on the surface of the material and make the layer on the surface of the specimen harder due to a denser microstructure due to carbon accumulation and the formation of other compounds such as carbides and carbon binding by crystal defects.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, the conclusions obtained are:

1. Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out, there has been a change in the mechanical properties of the local sprocket which has been carried out by the pack carburizing process and holding time variations. The specimen with a holding time of 15 minutes had a layer thickness of 265.77 μm , a hardness value of 405.84 HV and a wear rate of 0.000360 gr/minute; the specimen with a holding time of 30 minutes had a layer thickness of 346.55 μm , a hardness value of 188.81 HV and a wear rate of 0.000257 gr/minute; the specimen with a holding time of 45 minutes had a layer thickness of 935.47 μm , a hardness value of 277.37 HV and a wear rate of 0.000243 gr/minute; the specimen with a holding time of 60 minutes had a layer thickness of 452.42 μm , a hardness value of 407.44 HV and a wear rate of 0.000097 gr/minute

2. From the test results it was found that the local sprocket specimen that was packed carburized with a holding time of 60 minutes had the highest mechanical properties with a layer thickness of 452.42 μm , a hardness value of 407.44 HV and the lowest wear rate or highest wear resistance, namely 0.000097 gr/minute. These results have shown an increase in the mechanical properties of the specimen so that the quality of local sprockets approaches or even exceeds the quality of original Japanese manufactured sprockets but at a relatively cheap price.

References

- [1] Rahmi Yati, *Pengguna Sepeda Motor Indonesia Nomor 3 Terbanyak di Dunia, Ini Dampak Negatifnya*. (2021, September22):
[<https://ekonomi.bisnis.com/read/20210922/98/1445254/pengguna-sepeda-motor-indonesia-nomor-3-terbanyak-di-dunia-ini-dampak-negatifnya>] (Diakses tanggal: 20 Maret 2023).
- [2] Zafar Husain, Successful technology collaborations in automobile industry – strategic implications for firms indeveloping countries, *Int. J. Strategic Business Alliances*, Vol. 3, No. 4, 2014
- [3] ASM Handbook Commitee, *ASM Handbook Volume 4 Heat Treating*, Ohio, 1991
- [4] Budi Hartono Setiamarga, et. al., *Jurnal Teknik Mesin*, Vol. 21, No. 1, April 2006
- [5] ABDUL KARIM, et.al., Analisis Peningkatkan Kualitas Sproket Sepeda Motor Buatan Lokal Dengan Metode Karburasi, Tesis S2 Mag.Sistem Teknik University of Gajah mada
- [6] Faizal Akbar, Y., & Novi Sukma, D. (2021): *Pengaruh Waktu Tahan Pada Proses Carburizing Terhadap Kekerasan Baja AISI 1025 Dengan Perlakuan Pendinginan Quenching, Annealing, Dan Normalizing*. *Teknik Mesin*, 3,129–136.
- [7] S.A. Afolalu, et. al., Impacts of Carburizing Temperature and Holding Time on Wear of High Speed Steel Cutting Tools, *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Volume 6, Issue 5, May-2015, ISSN 2229-5518
- [8] Yahya, et.al., The Carburizing Process of Low Carbon Steel with Charcoal Media, *JOURNAL OF*

MECHANICALSCIENCE AND ENGINEERINGVol.1 No.1 October 2013

- [9] Agustinus Deka Betan, et. al., Effect of Carburizing Temperature and Holding Time on Mechanical Properties Low Carbon Steel Using Schleichera Oleosa Carbonized Chorcoal, ICESC 2019, October 18-19, Indonesia Copyright © 2019 EAI DOI 10.4108/eai.18-10-2019.2289858
- [10] Nanulaitta, N. J. M., &Patty, A. A. (2011): *Analisis Perbandingan Komposisi Karbon Dan Bubuk Tulang Sapi Dalam Proses Karburasi Padat Untuk Mendapatkan Nilai Kekerasan Tertinggi Pada Baja Karbon S-35C*.
- [11] Abidah, A. F., & Drastiawati, N. S. (2019): *Analisis SS400 Hasil Carburizing Media Arang TempurungKelapa-BaCO₃ dengan Variasi Temperatur Pemanasan dan Holding Time Ditinjau dari Pengujian Kekerasan dan Struktur Mikro Analisis SS400 Hasil Carburizing Media Arang Tempurung Kelapa-BaCO₃ Dengan Variasi Temperatur Pemanasan Dan Holding Time Ditinjau Dari Pengujian Kekerasan Dan StrukturMikro*.
- [12] ASMHandbookCommitee,ASMHandbookVolume9*MetallographyandMicrostructures* , 1992
- [13] Fatai Olufemi Aramide, et. al., Effects of Carburization Time and Temperature on the Mechanical Properties of Carburized Mild Steel, Using Activated Carbon as Carburizer, Materials Research, Vol. 12, No. 4, 483-487, 2009
- [14] Y Bontong, et.al., BEHAVIOR OF PACK CARBURIZING WITH BONE BUFFALOCHARCOAL AND BACO₃ AGAINST MECHANICALPROPERTIES OF LOW CARBON STEEL, Materials Research, Vol. 12, No. 4, 483-487, 2009
- [15] O.Adedipe, et.al., Sustainable carburization of low carbon steel using organic additives: A review, Sustainable Materials and TechnologiesVolume 38,December 2023, e00723

A Brief Author Biography

1st Author Carolus Bintoro– I was born June 2 1962, in Jogjakarta Indonesia. In 1986 he had the opportunity to study in France and in 1997 he had the opportunity to take a master's course at ITB in the field of aeroelastic and continue to take a doctoral degree in the field of vibration. And now I continue my research activities in the field of renewable energy, Vibration, Composite Material